

Nation – National Defence and Security – Introduction

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Forewords

The society of a new democracy has become aware of the responsibility for the preservation of the country's independence. The growing development of nations must be accompanied by the increase in the preparation of its defense against threats and aggressions. The planning of actions for National Defense, in charge of the State, has its highest conditioning document in the National Defense Policy, which establishes the National Defense Objectives.

The first of these is the guarantee of sovereignty, of national patrimony and of territorial integrity. Other objectives include the structuring of Armed Forces with adequate organizational and operational capabilities and the creation of social and economic conditions to support National Defense, as well as the contribution to international peace and security and the protection of national interests at different levels projection of the country.

The Nation

National defense strategy is inseparable from national development strategy. This motivates that. That provides shield for this. Each reinforces the reasons of the other. In both, one awakens to nationality and builds the Nation.

Throughout its existence, Man is confronted with an extensive range of material needs and cultural and spiritual interests and aspirations. Needs, interests and aspirations form the basis of human action, stimulating or restricting individual activities. As a result of the presence of rationality in these activities, it is necessary for Man to establish his own objectives and the planning of aches in order to reach them.

Living side by side with his fellow man, he discovers that he has in common a series of needs, interests and aspirations. As you identify these common bonds, there is naturally a feeling that, through joint action, you can make your individual and collective action more effective. Group goals then emerge as a reference for the action of the social group.

The origin of the different groups that integrate a Nation is linked to the diversity of needs, interests and aspirations that, in each place and time, congregate its members.

The **idea of the Nation** presupposes the continuous sedimentation, throughout the generations, of a common perspective of integration and temporal harmony, where both the individuals and the social groups, although different, when observed in the spatial dimension, identify each other by commune of a stable cultural reality, because it contains the feeling, individual and collective, of a common origin and destination.

Among the most important social groups are family, professionals, religious, politicians, community, leisure, ethnic and regional, which induce their integral definition of goals, sometimes differentiated or even conflicting.

As society and the Nation develop, the groups that integrate them also modify their structures, redefine their values, interests, aspirations and thus their objectives, thus maintaining the dynamism characteristic of all historical-cultural complexes. From a broad perspective, one can distinguish, in relation to social groups, different types of interests, as well as affinities or similarities, such as:

- **Survival**, representing the common desire to maintain the existence and vitality of the group;
- **Expansion**, related to the desire for expansion and strengthening; - cohesion, expressing the desire and the need for internal harmony, through the reduction of conflicts;
- Of **influence**, translating the will to change the behaviour of other groups with which it relates, for the benefit of their own interests; and integration, representing the need to establish identity awareness among its components.

The historical-cultural evolution of the national community, by promoting the integration of distinct social groups, generates the emergence of values, needs, interests and aspirations that transcend group, sector and regional particularities and, at the same time, accordingly individual and collective actions.

The needs, the greatest revelation of human dissatisfaction, are first identified in the individual and hence serve as a reference for groups and the Nation itself. Collective desires, awakened by the needs of the whole nation, consciously or unconsciously represent the impulse to show the sense of present dignity as a constant in the process of realization of Man, for this process, when based on values, makes the national community the privileged space of inter-human exchanges that lead to improvement.

These desires will boost the service of interests and aspirations. National interests find their essentiality in values of internal and external nature, representing a relationship between the national group and something that it believes indispensable, in time and in asparagus, to define such interests in appropriate conditions. They are one of the most important imperatives in the life of any State, because they stimulate the Nation to build its future.

Alongside national interests, and at a deeper level, as a true integrating dimension emanating from the national consciousness, are national aspirations. These and those may be clothed with such a meaning that they end up confusing themselves with the fate of nationality. In this condition, they become vital, since they bind the survival, identity and evolution of the Nation as such. The ultimate synthesis resulting from meeting these needs, interests and aspirations and what can be called **Common Good**.

In order to better orient these efforts, the Common Ground is translated as a synthesis objective of the **National Objectives**, when they are more explicit points of reference capable of responding to the project that the Nation has of its destiny. Government, identify the ways that the governments, acting in the name of the Nation, have the best for the conquest and maintenance of the first.

National Objectives (NO) result from the identification of needs, interests and aspirations that, at a certain stage of their historical-cultural revolution, the Nation seeks to satisfy.

The universality of the primary needs of the human being and the similarity of the existential conditions of the nations determine the characterization of some national Objectives common to almost all the communities.

The maintenance of objectives is culturally distinct. Besides these, other objectives will be specifically established by the different Nations throughout their evolution, in the face of variables that act in the historical - cultural process.

The identification of these variables must take into account two classes of conditioning factors: internal and external. The first concerns the historical-cultural evolution of the national community; the second, the presence of the country in the international community, making it possible to understand how this reality interacts with the interests and aspirations born within the national culture.

Human Conditioning Factors

Human conditioning factors represent the basic variables in the process of nationality formation, since they express the dynamic elements of the national will. Among the human conditioners, two stand out: the national character and the elites.

Throughout the formation of the national community, different ethnic groups, with distinct cultural traits, are integrated, constituting a reality with their own characteristics. There are specific forms of thinking, feeling and acting that, at one point, constitute a significant basis for the political action of each people.

National character cannot be understood as generalization of individual traits. It follows from a historical-cultural process where the interaction of the elements that constitute the Nation gives it a dynamic character, evolving and transforming throughout this process.

Another determining factor for the identification and establishment of the National Objectives and represented by the elites in capturing and interpreting national interests and aspirations.

Elites are the sets of people who, in government, other different segments of national society, play leadership roles or represent collective needs, interests and aspirations.

This conduction or representation stems from a natural and legitimate process in which the community, by expressing its will, does so through the action of its members.

The components of the elites, despite their specific group ties, should not set objectives that are distanced from or conflicting with national aspirations, otherwise the community in the name of which they intend to act will be frustrated.

The identification of the Fundamental Objectives and the establishment of the Government Goals have in the environment another determining factor of fundamental importance.

Man's relationship with nature and his effort to transform it into wealth are of great relevance for setting Government objectives. Important is to use nature without destroying it, guaranteeing future generations the means of subsistence.

Territorial extension, geographic positioning, sufficiency, abundance or scarcity of natural resources, climate and relief limit or facilitate the formation of national identity. As nations are Mediterranean, island, tropical, temperate or cold, they have large or small territorial extension, abundance or lack of mineral wealth, having different objectives.

The great territorial extension is never homogeneous and the diversity of its regions demands caution in the identification and the establishment of authentic National Objectives.

Institutional Conditioning Factors

Institutions represent an integrated complex of ideas, feelings, norms, patterns of behaviour and interpersonal relationships, created to respond to the interests, needs and aspirations of a national community, reflecting, on the one hand, the cultural identity of a people, and on the other, the transformations that occur throughout the social-historical process.

Such transformations take place either for endogenous motives or as a result of contact and integrated with other cultures. From this contact can occur both the assimilation of exogenous traits, maintaining the identity of the national group, and a cultural shock, with the possible disappearance of **national identity**.

Institutions influence national development and stability, and can also be seen as the way in which they materialize.

International relations determine conditions or circumstances that amplify or restrict, that stimulate or limit the power and prestige of nations and influence the outcome of cooperation, competence and conflict between them in all sectors of human activity. When analyzing the emergence and development of the Nations, some are found to be expanding, others at steady state and others in decadence. These situations represent constraints to the identification and establishment of the National Objectives.

Whatever level the nations are in the context of international relations, what is projected is their interests and aspirations. Thus, in the field of reciprocal influences, each nation seeks to conquer and maintain its objectives or preserve its legitimate interests, which, by the way, contributes so much to the existence of areas of cooperation as to competition or, on the other hand, to the emergence or exacerbation of conflicts.

The determining factors of the National Objectives are not exhausted within the limits of the internal relations of the national community, having deep interaction between them and those coming from abroad, in a process of mutual influence.

The Fundamental Objectives (FO) are not established or fixed. They are originated from the historical-cultural process and naturally emerge as the needs and interests of the community crystallized into the national consciousness, representing aspirations that, regardless of class, region, creed, political ideologies, ethnic origins or other attributes, to all brothers

The Fundamental Objectives must be identified and, for this identification, an important role is the elites, who are responsible for realizing national interests and aspirations.

Reflecting the ongoing process of socio-cultural and institutional change, the Fundamental Objectives represent the major framework to guide all planning at the national level.

For the correct understanding of the meaning of each Fundamental Objective, it is necessary to characterize, based on the historical evolution of the Nation and on the actions of its elites, besides examining the human, physical, institutional and external conditioning factors, creating perceptions, differentiated.

Democracy

Democracy, as a Fundamental Objective, has two essential meanings:

- The incessant search for a society that promotes a lifestyle identified by respect for the dignity of the person, for freedom and equal opportunities.

- The adoption of a political regime which is fundamentally characterized by:

- * Continuous improvement of institutions and political representation, as well as their adaptation to the needs of the national reality; and the legitimacy of the exercise of political power, through majority rule and respect for minorities.

- Organization of a rule of law, meaning:

* Participation of society in the conduct of public life; guarantee of fundamental human rights; party plurality; Division and harmony between the powers of the State (Executive, Legislative and Judicial):

* Responsibility of governors and governed by the conduct of political action; and,

* Alternation in power.

National Integration

National Integration is the consolidation of the national community, with solidarity among its members, without prejudices or disparities of any kind, aiming at its conscious and growing participation in all sectors of national life and in the common effort to preserve the values of nationality and reduce regional and social imbalances. Integration consists of the incorporation of the entire territory into the political and socio-economic context of the Nation.

Integrity of National Heritage

Integrity of National Heritage consists in the territorial integrity, the patrimonial sea, the contiguous zone, the exclusive economic zone and the continental shelf, as well as the overlying airspace. Integrity of public goods, natural resources and the environment, preserved from predatory exploitation. Integrity of the historical-cultural heritage represented by the language, customs and traditions, in short, the preservation of the national identity.

Social peace

In the view of a society that cultivates spiritual values, peace is a necessary condition and desired effect. Social Peace reflects a value of life, not imposed, but derived from consensus, in search of a society characterized by the conciliation and harmony between people and groups, especially between capital and labour, and by a sense of social justice that guarantees the satisfaction of the minimum needs of each citizen, valuing the potentialities of life in common, benefiting each one, as well as the whole of society.

Progress

Progress is a finding based on the past and the present: it takes the facts as a basis, but it projects itself in the future as an objective. In this approach, it has, among others, the following characteristics:

- Adequate economic growth;

- Fair distribution of income;

- Moral and spiritual perfection of man;
- Ability to provide security;
- High standards of living;
- Ethics and effectiveness in the political sphere; and,
- Constant scientific and technological progress.

Sovereignty

Sovereignty means maintaining the intangibility of the Nation, ensuring the capacity for self-determination and coexisting with the other Nations in terms of equality of rights, not accepting any form of intervention in their internal affairs, nor participation in acts of this nature in relation to other Nations. Sovereignty also means the supremacy of the legal order of the National State throughout the territory.

The constitutional value that is most under threat is, of course, sovereignty itself. Sovereignty is being weakened as the forces of globalization ensure that forces outside the walls of the state fundamentally affect, and sometimes determine, what goes on within them.

Sovereignty and the consequential ban on intervention are also being undermined normatively. As an essentially Westphalia construct, modern ideas of sovereignty predate the Enlightenment by one hundred years. The greatest threat to sovereignty and the associated stigma attached to intervention lies in the full implementation of Enlightenment values.

There were many reasons for this limited role of Enlightenment values in international law. Initially, democratic nations sought the protection of sovereignty against autocratic states that might intervene to crush their fledgling democracies. Their inclination was to keep domestic political values out of international law lest the major views of other states (for example, in favour of monarchies) might be imposed on them. Democrats were only too aware that the French Revolution and the revolutions of 1848 were defeated by autocrats allied to the regimes which the new democracies had ousted.

With the notable exception of US interventions in the Americas, virtually all interventions during this century have been by autocratic states -and the enlightenment credentials of most US interventions in the Americas were dubious, to say the least. It is only recently that the majority of nation states came to enjoy any real measure of democracy and it becomes possible to think of international law being reflective of liberal democratic ideals.

The glaring inconsistency between the bases of constitutional legitimacy in domestic and international law has been sustained by a number of factors:

1. **The idea that international law is a law for all states, of which not all are democracies.**
2. **Cultural relativist notions that different cultures have different approaches to governance.**
3. **The understanding that it is necessary to 'do business' in both commercial and political terms with a particular territory and that the only way to do this is through the group which exercises effective power in that territory.**
4. **The idea that there is no alternative to political authority based on the prior successful use of force in a state where there has never been a democratic government which can speak for the people.** Even where a democratic government is ousted, it may not be able to retain the integrity of its representative principles for long (as it becomes difficult to collect all elected representatives in one place and it is impossible to conduct new elections).
5. **The regretful history of interventions.** Nations will rarely intervene solely for the benefit of the citizens of another nation state. They will only do so if it is in their interests. The danger is that nations will intervene to further their interests on the pretext of helping the citizens of the target state, but their 'assistance' will actually work to the detriment of those citizens.

Intervening nations generally intervene in the name of international law but are rarely willing to subject themselves to it. For all these reasons, liberal democrats are traditionally wary of interventions and sceptical of their ability to achieve further liberal democratic values.

At present, international legal personality involves the right of those in power to contract on behalf of the state and the people who are within its territory. Even when a contract is beyond the legal power of the rulers, even if it is corruptly entered into and the benefits are corruptly appropriated; its provisions bind the successors to those rulers.

Sovereign debt is incurred by corrupt regimes and the proceeds are spirited away to bank accounts in the developed world. When a democratic regime replaces the former rulers, it is forced to pay back the debt to the lenders – while the corrupt former leaders enjoy the loan funds from the comfort and security of their First World exile.

The paradigm shift would fundamentally change the dynamics of such arrangements. If a government is not accountable to all of its citizens, then the people are not accountable for the actions of the government. When the international debt collectors call, the people can legitimately claim: 'You did not contract with us, you contracted with them. Look to recover your funds from those to whom you lent them.'

They could insist on the principle that governments could not commit those whose consent they had not sought and those to whom they were not accountable. This would make international law look more like domestic law. If hoodlums take over a house and hold the lawful owners in terror, they commit serious offenses. If they seek to borrow from a bank on the security of the house, the loan is not only unenforceable against the owners, the bank is also guilty of some very serious conspiracy offenses, especially if they knew that the money was being used to buy new guns to terrorise the occupants.

Far from having their loans repaid by the occupants, they would be facing enormous damages claims, prison sentences and almost certain closure. Not suggesting that international bankers should suffer these kinds of consequences. All that is suggested is that, as a matter of international law, there should be no obligation on the new government to repay the loan. The inevitable consequence, that loan funds would dry up for all but democracies, rendering dictatorial regimes economically no viable, is fully intended!

Cheating does not count in this and in all other matters, the government's power to claim to represent a group of people and to make commitments in their name would be dependent on its having gained the people's consent. By making recognition dependent on such consent, it will be in the interest of governments to gain it. It also has the wonderful side effect of ensuring that cheating does not count.

This assumes minimum standards for fair elections. These are being formulated for UN supervised elections. These minimum standards could be developed in a number of ways:

- by developing practice in UN supervised elections,

- by international nongovernmental organizations,

- by the formation of a 'Democratic League' with rules for admission, and,

- ultimately, when this principle is established in international law, by international law making bodies like the UN General Assembly and by the International Court of Justice.

The limited but growing recognition of the possibility of intervention on humanitarian grounds is the first crack in the arguments used to support the principle of no intervention. In addition, as more and more nations formally embrace democratic ideals, the first two factors listed above are losing much of their force.

As most countries want to trade with the outside world, the third factor becomes a two-edged sword would-be intervenient may be less dependent on bilateral trade than the states which are the targets of intervention. The problems referred to in the fourth factor are not as insurmountable as they might once have seemed (as evidenced by, for example, the fact that the African National Congress (ANC) was seen in many international forums as the legitimate voice of the black majority of South Africa).

The final factor remains an important one and the resolution of this inconsistency depends on the development of constitutional theory and the development of new institutions, the reform of old institutions and/or the increased utilization of existing institutions.

Nonetheless, within 10-20 years, the prior successful use of force will be as contemptible a claim to recognition in international law as it is within the domestic constitutional law of existing democracies.

Within 20 years, it will be impracticable for authoritarian regimes to overthrow democratic regimes because of the consequent denial of recognition and, to a lesser extent, because the intervention of others will 'be unequivocally sanctioned. During that period, the justification for what we would now call 'intervention' will have been properly worked out as part of the emerging international constitutional jurisprudence.

The full acceptance of this principle means that a government only represents internationally those whose consent it has sought and gained. This would involve little change for democratic regimes. For undemocratic regimes it would mean that the government would be seen as representing only those whose consent it has sought, be it a party, an ethnic group or a restricted franchise.

This allows no democratic regimes to be recognized as representing one or more groups within the geographical area of the relevant state with a current capacity to dominate other groups. However, a government that has not sought a mandate from a group of people would not be seen as speaking for those so excluded.

This leaves obvious lacunae for those whose consent the government has not sought. It opens the way for others to claim to represent those whose consent has not been sought by the government. In some cases, such credentials would be easily established. Where a democratically elected government is ousted in a military coup, members of that government or their accredited representatives still at large would speak for that government.

In most cases, it is not nearly so clear who will have the right to speak for those whose consent the government has not sought. It is part of the nature of dictatorships and oligarchies that they will use force to prevent and intimidate the processes by which such credentials could be established.

There will usually be a number of voices claiming to speak for the unrepresented in a number of overlapping ways. Sometimes, there will be a body that represents the bulk of the people in one sphere of life that comes to speak more broadly -such as the Catholic Church in communist Poland and COSATU in South Africa.

This means that the excluded will not speak with a strong, clear and unified voice. However, that is no reason for not listening to them. In particular, those who try to suppress those

voices have no standing to suggest that the lack of clarity should be held against those voices which can still be heard.

State Secrecy

According to the well-known definition of the sociologist Edward Shils 1996: 26), a secret is a compulsory retention of knowledge, reinforced by the prospect of punishment in case of revelation. This definition is only in part equivalent to other current definitions in the specialized literature such as that of Sissela Bok (1982: 051) who claims to be a secret anything kept intentionally hidden.

Emphasizing this intentional aspect of secrecy as being a property of information that is hidden from the knowledge of others, Kim Lane Scheppele uses a very concise and comprehensive formulation: A secret is a piece of information. that is intentionally untold by one or more social actor (s) from one or more social actor (s)." The problem of Scheppele's definition (which is basically the same as Bok's) is that it is too far-reaching for the purposes of the discussion to be made about intelligence and secrecy.

Scheppele recognizes that the intentional retention of information in the relationship between two or more social actors varies according to the contexts of the interaction, but its definition does not allow us to differentiate between **private secrets and public interests**.

The Shils approach is preferable because it maintains the idea of intentionality and adds an external regulatory element for the retention of information: **the punishment legally established in the case of revelation**. Public secrecy is thus distinct from any information that is privately kept secret, which is nothing more than a voluntary retention of knowledge reinforced by the indifference of others.

In this somewhat paradoxical sense, secrets are a form of public regulation of information flows.

There are at least five categories of information regulated by public secrecy:

- 1) **National defense;**
- 2) **Foreign policy;**
- 3) **Legal proceedings;**
- 4) **Intellectual property and patents;**
- 5) **Privacy of citizens.**

The public justification for the need for secrecy varies greatly in each category. Of the five categories, the first two contain most of the information kept secret based on national security considerations.

This is the kind of public secret that will be dealt with in that section of the text. It is worth noting that the justification of secrecy based on the potential risk to national security is not

available to private actors, but only to the State and its representatives and even in special situations.

Government secrets are compatible with the principle of transparency of governmental acts only when the justification of their need can be made, itself in public. This is what David Luban (1996: 154-198) calls the first-order order and second-order maxims relative to the principle of transparency.

A non-aprioristic defence of this concept involves admitting the government's secrecy about norms, procedures, and policies (first-order maxims) as long as the reasons for the secret regulation of such information (maxims of second order) can be publicly exposed and justified.

Nothing prevents however, that the third or fourth order maxima be adopted by governments or intelligence services to justify apodictically a decision to keep secret the very reasons why they keep certain policies secret. That is as in the case of national security, there are no definitive antidotes against abusing the use of government secrecy. At the limit, it must be admitted that this is a kind of powerful regulation based on trust.

However, precisely because the excessive use of third-order maxims leads to non legitimating and cynicism over the very institutions that one wishes to protect through secrecy, a democratic regime must try to translate the moral principle of transparency into propositions of institutional design. In the end, government secrecy may be compatible with the principle of transparency only when decisions about the application of this type of regulation to certain information flows are made through publicly established institutional mechanisms in the context of democratic rules of the game.

In the areas of government action related to national defence and foreign policy, the main justification for restricting the circulation of information produced or maintained by the government is the potential harm that its appropriation by a third party (e.g. a foreign government could cause state security and, as a consequence, to the individual security of the members of the community, for example, **weapons systems, contingency plans and mobilization, scientific and technological research of military application, intentions in negotiations of international agreements, performance of defensive capacities** and other similar things, once known by an adversary or enemy, increase our vulnerabilities and provide a crucial comparative advantage for opponents in conflicting interactions.

In addition to being necessary for purely defensive reasons, the secret is often also crucial for governments to plan, implement, and complete military and diplomatic missions.

An obvious example of the crucial role of secrecy is the temptation to surprise in military attacks, but one can also argue in the same direction as the success of sensitive diplomatic negotiations (for example, the secret negotiations between China and the United States that preceded Nixon's visit to Beijing in 1972, or the secret negotiations between Palestinian and

Israeli representatives that preceded the so-called Oslo Accords in 1993). In such cases, the justification for secrecy is based more on the need to prevent government objectives from being frustrated by the early disclosure of information than on potential national security damage.

The need for secrecy is also claimed in intergovernmental deliberation processes on the domestic issues considered relevant to national security (energy, transport, policing, etc.), decision-making processes, the premature disclosure of divergences of opinion within of the government could be harmful to the safety of operations and to the possibility of success of any of the goals and plans eventually chosen. In these cases, the applications of secrecy restrictions are much more problematic in legal and, mainly, political terms from the point of view of democracy.

A final general justification for state secrecy is the need to protect the identities and confidential relationships of governing agencies with certain individuals, groups, and governments.

The need for secrecy in these relationships emerges from a variety of contexts and takes diverse forms, although the most obvious case is just the protection of sources and methods in the intelligence area.

In addition to the risk of life for the individuals themselves and their families, the exposure of this type of relationship through the failure of one party to maintain secrecy has chain effects on the future cooperation provision, which is considered to be harmful for the national security and for the prospect of the realization of governmental interests and policies in the international arena.

Apart from public justification of their practical necessity and moral validity, state secrets would not remain secret if they were counted only with the discretion of individuals who share the secretive information or with the indifference of others. The protection of State secrets is based on three complementary processes:

- 1) **Classification procedures,**
- 2) **Access controls,** and
- 3) **Punishments** in case of unauthorized disclosure.

In the first case, legally competent authorities identify information sets that are sensitive to national security and apply classification rules that define the degree of secrecy required and the intensity of the physical restriction measures for each reporting.

Safety classifications are made by assigning external markers that define the importance of each information for national security (typically, the categories of confidential, secret and ultra-secret).

The attribution of a specific marker for a document or set of information is done - in theory - by a legally authorized official or body. In the case of information considered extremely vital for national security, for example, the assignment of the category of top secret can only be done by the highest authority in the country or by its express delegation.

The secrecy categories also provide for access restriction corresponding to the degree of confidentiality assigned, that is, the more secretive information is, the longer it will elapse until it is fully publicized.

In the second block of measures (access controls), measures of physical restriction on access to such information imply surveillance, management, storage and transmission systems, no matter in what specific media the information is.

The security discipline of information systems) is concerned not only with the cryptography of messages and information repositories, but increasingly with the reduction of systemic vulnerabilities of production, storage and communication networks. However, it is important to ensure that sensitive information of different categories is intercepted by unauthorized users (or by spying, or that may be altered or destroyed (sabotage).

Additional safeguards for the preservation of government secrets are obtained through access veto systems for unauthorized persons, as well as the avoidance of additional restrictions on the circulation of sensitive information through the application of the principle known as "need to know" - "need to-know-only".

Veto systems involve the application of security screening procedures for all persons applying for employment in government agencies in the area of defence, intelligence, and security. In areas considered critical to national security, safety controls are applied to both civil and military employees as well as employees of private companies who maintain contracts with government agencies.

In the case of intelligence agencies in addition to the standardized checks on criminal records and credit and health records, more detailed interviews with relatives, neighbours and acquaintances about the individual's past are carried out, as well as the application of special tests with "lie detectors" (Polygraph tests).

After successfully passing veto and investigation systems to gain access to 'classified' information, public servants must obtain credentials corresponding to the classification level of the information (reserved, confidential, secret and top secret).

In general, the level of access depends on the degree of seniority of the official and / or the importance of the position held. It should be noted that, once the access credential has been granted, it does not accompany the official or elected official regardless of the positions he occupies. Periodic security checks are, at least in theory, necessary for the renewal of access credentials.

However, drastic the security procedures for granting credentials are, access to government secrets also depends on the application of the principle of segmentation of the most sensitive information. Needlessly, this principle says that each document or set of information can be accessed only by employees who effectively need to know about their content, not by anyone who has an access credential with compatible classification level.

This generates new external markers and additional restrictions for access In the case of the United States classification system, for example, in addition to the three top security categories confidential, secret and top secret, about fifty additional markers which, while not having the same legal status, often establish tighter regulation than the formal system. Programs, information and documents with special access special shared with information may be established on the basis of the "need to know" principle. In the third block of measures, if safety procedures fail, the dissuasive elements that differentiate Edward Shils definition of public secrecy: administrative and legal penalties come into play. In this case, it is important to differentiate the obtaining of secrets through the espionage of mere leakage of confidential information to the public.

According to Lustgarten and Leigh (1994: 221-248), because it is a discreet and / or stealthy action, successful espionage opens a breach in the secure information that the government is slow to realize or even aware of in favour of a foreign government, regardless of its motivations (ideology, money, blackmail, revenge, etc.), as a he cannot claim the common good of the nation he is spying on, nor can he claim the humanity as a whole to justify his action.

Whether it is a recruited agent (citizen or permanent resident), or his foreign controller (who may have diplomatic cover or not), the act of spying is an action that alters the distribution of international power and betrays trust on which citizenship is based. In a world of states that need to defend themselves, espionage is a criminalized conduct in most legal orders.

In the United States, for example, depending on the severity of the case, espionage can be punished by the jury with life imprisonment or even the death penalty. Even if many spies are not even prosecuted, which is true even for intrinsic reasons the very logic of counterintelligence operations, the point to be highlighted is that the seriousness with which the debate is viewed contrasts with the relative trivialization of the leaks of confidential information in democracies.

The cause of this phenomenon lies in the understanding of the jurisprudence that unauthorized disclosure of confidential information relatively less damage than splattering because the publicity of information immediately alerts the government and triggers countermeasures and attempts to control damages.

It may also be that unauthorized disclosure of classified information has been accidental, or that it has been intentionally motivated by the decision to expose some corruption, arbitrary or governmental incompetence that was being concealed through the formal rules of public secrecy.

In such cases, even if the motivation of the agent making the information public makes a difference for the assessment of its credibility, the damage to national security must be contrasted with the eventual public benefit resulting from the transgression. Obviously, this is always controversial and attempts at legal regulation of the phenomenon run counter to its political complexity.

In most cases that appear to be in the media, in fact, leakage of sensitive information ("leakage is a power resource used by members of the government itself to launch trial balloons on policies and projects to torpedo a policy they disagree with In the United States, the inflow of classified information is penalized by administrative measures (from censorship to loss of office or employment), cash fines and up to ten years' imprisonment).

In the United States, however, the relative importance of leakage of classified information by high-ranking members of the central government tends to generate, on the one hand, public discredit for the need to operate classification systems and, on the other hand, a defensive reaction from the security organs that can be described such as hyper-classification. Incidentally, failures in any of the three processes described in the foregoing paragraphs tend to generate excessive expansion in the other two as a kind of perverse "compensation."

Be that as it may, the central government is a form of regulation of flows of information widely used in the State with temporary. As in almost everything in the area of intelligence studies, the empirical data available refer to the case of the United States, with reliability untested and known to be difficult to compare as a function of scale.

In the final report of the committee set up by Congress to amend the "Protection and Reduction of Government Secrecy", 1971, it appears that only documents classified more than twenty-five years of that year totalled more than 1.5 billion pages. The total amount of classified documents is not known.

It is estimated that in a single year 192, all states reported 6.1 million pages of classified documents. About 99% of the original classifications are made in five federal government bodies 153% in the Department of Defence. 30% in the CIA, 10% in the Department of Justice, 30% in the State Department and 3% in the Department of Energy).

The weight of the intelligence agencies in the formation of the United States' secret system of government is very clear, which can be extrapolated to the other States with temporary working hypotheses.

As Michael Herman 1961 reminds us, the relationship between secrecy and intelligence, by means of the operation of information-gathering operations in intelligence, is precisely to obtain information that cannot be obtained (or is difficult to access) through ordinary means of search.

To put it in the most emphatic and somewhat exaggerated terms of Kenneth Robertson (1987), intelligence activity is first and foremost an attempt to discover the secrets of others through use of mere secrets. In fact, Michael Herman is most cautious in considering that the rationale of intelligence secrecy rests on three different kinds of consideration regarding sources, information, operations, methods, and technologies employed.

In the first place, secrecy is used as a form of regulation when the value of the intelligence obtained depends on the target not knowing what is actually known under it. For example, prior knowledge of an enemy plan for a surprise attack opens the possibility of setting up an ambush. But this is only possible if the enemy does not know that the victimized attacks will be attacked.

Secondly, the secret also stems from the precarious legal status of the methods employed to collect intelligence. Especially in times of peace, espionage, electronic surveillance and hacking of computer networks are contrary to the laws of countries / targets and even international laws that guarantee the inviolability of territory, airspace and territorial waters. The political costs of these violations can be undermined through secrecy, which also allows more effective diplomatic management of eventual crises.

In third place the strongest reason for the secrecy and vulnerability of the sources to the security countermeasures that the target would take if they knew of the opponent's effort at intelligence. In any case, what is intended to be protected through secrecy is not any particular information that a source has already provided, but rather the continuity of intelligence flows.

In war and peace, secrets profoundly mark the "modus operandi" and organizational culture of the intelligence service, even when the work of analysis is primarily based on ostensible, non-secret sources. It should be noted that there is no direct and univocal relationship between the secret nature of the sources and means of collection and the analyzes produced in intelligence. There are, however, negative associations between the intensity / quantity of government secrets and the possibility of citizens' control over government.

Therefore, from the point of view of democratic institutional arrangements, the application of this type of regulation to a specific information flow would have a double burden of proof: that of the need for secrecy the effectiveness of the mission and the guarantee of public control, albeit indirect.

External Control:

Citizens' access to information about what rulers do and what they know is a necessary condition for keeping contemporary governments minimally representative of the governed.

One of the main dilemmas faced by democratic theory is how to reconcile the necessary autonomy that rulers prescribe to defend the interests and security of the governed, with the full functioning of mechanisms capable of ensuring that the actions of the rulers will be conducted respecting the will of the governed.

This respect is as much relative to the will expressly expressed by the governed as it is relative to the later evaluation of the actions of the governors by the governed (accountability).

This dilemma is particularly difficult when it comes to discussing public control over national security, government secrecy, and intelligence. This is because, in such cases, the tensions between state security and individual security, such as the tensions between government secrecy and the citizens' right to information are structurally determined by the anarchic nature of authority in the international system and are more or less acute depending on the nature of the political regimes, forms of government and other institutional characteristics and political choices of the relevant subjects in each country.

Although they can and should be reduced through conscious political action and careful institutional construction, such tensions are unavoidable within the framework of the present state system, which represents the predominant modern way of solving the problem of institutional accommodation in complex societies marked by conflicts of interest and opinions.

In relation to the existence and operation of state intelligence and security services, the double tension discussed in the previous sections implies two types of main risks:

- 1) **The risk of government manipulation of services seeking to maximize power;**
- 2) **The risk of self-assessment of the services themselves,** which would be transformed into a kind of parallel power within the State.

Generally in the area of intelligence and security the mechanisms of public control are quite fragile and uncertain, and the more indirect and horizontal tend to be relatively more effective.

Faced with this relative fragility, it is common to find exhortations about the need for training programs and socialization processes for officials of intelligence agencies that incorporate high civic values and a high degree of professionalism and **respect for the Constitution.**

National Security

Security can be a relative condition of protection in which is capable of neutralizing perceptible acts with the existence of someone or something with reasonable expectation of success.

A safe and secure organization is achieved through standards and protection for defined sets of information, systems, facilities, communications, personnel, equipment or operations.

Protective measures should retain some proportionality in perceived threats its existence, effectiveness and autonomy of who - or what - is being protected. In the absence of proportionality, the pursuit of security becomes itself the effectiveness, autonomy and, in the limit, the very existence of the "object" of the protection.

The proportionality requirement is a tricky point in the notion of safety while an absolute condition of the existence of a measure or method of uncertainty. The total protection of everything and / or of all, against everything and / or all, is something not impossible in an intellectual and psychological perspective but the more undesirable is totalitarian security.

Having this clear is crucial to starting any discussion on National security.

For national security, it is understood as a relative condition of collective and individual protection of the members of a society against to their survival and autonomy. In this sense, the term refers to the vital dimension of individual and collective existence in the context of modern society of societies, delimited by national states of territorial territory.

In the limit, being safe in this context means living in a State which is reasonably able to neutralize vital through negotiation, obtaining information on skills and intentions, through the use of extraordinary measures and the range of options relating to the employment of forces.

The double face of these threats, internal and external, implies some degree of complementarily and integration between foreign policies, defence and public order.

The national security can be obtained through public policies. Is the main expression for the exercise of sovereignty having the State the monopoly of the force.

The vast majority of institutional orders recognize military aggression, spying, covert operations, and economic blockade as vital external forces, capable of generating proportionate dissuasive responses on the part of threatened states.

Internal threats characteristically, are the internal support to those external factors, plus the problematic notion of "their subversion". In the last decade, appeared a new category of transnational of threats such as organized crime, drug trafficking and terrorism.

Despite the definition of national security and legal delimitation of the threats, it is important to note that the means of the term and its practical consequences have extremely variations in different political contexts and institutions.

Far from solving problems, any definition is a precarious starting point for reflection. In fact, the insistence on an abstract concept and the temporal of national security, applicable to all contexts and circuits, becomes part of the problem, since it tends to separate arbitrarily between the so-called "low" policy the conflicts of opinion and interests of what would be the "high" policy on security and the problems of force in relations between States (and also in social relations within states).

Generally, this persistence on the absolute concept of national security tends to "automatically" depoliticize the concept, disavowing itself discussion on the topic.

In democratic regimes it takes an effort in the direction, bringing the themes of security, defence, intelligence and policing for the regular agenda of political issues.

There are, of course, restrictions for ISS, especially those related to government secrecy. But there is no reason to think that such kind of purity that precludes theoretical or empirical research in this important area of State action.

An important step in advancing the security discussion can be given by evaluating two recent attempts to their perception of the impact of national security by:

1) The successful attempt to resolve the tension between state security and individual security by the strictly juridical and normative way. That has been the typical liberal position in the international debate and, although contribute to an assessment of the inevitable risks to democracy, the operation of organizations of strength and intelligence responsible for the national security, has been unable to go beyond delimitation of the threats are considered legally valid for that a government can claim reasons of "national security" for its acts.

2) The number of attempts to solve the moral bigoted of the concept national security system through the use of the concept of human security. The criticism of this attempt will have a more accurate assessment of the risks of loss of efficiency in the operation of the armed forces and the intelligence services, especially in excessive expansion of the range of defensive requirements and information on the adoption of the concept of human security.

Barry Buzan 1999 1: 35-56) and Charles Tilley and 1998: 397-4 121, argue that security relations are inextricable between the different levels of analysis (systemic, state and individual) of international relations.

The international system as a whole, its regional and functional systems, unitary actors such as States or intergovernmental organizations, with government agencies and social groups, or more individuals, affect the safety of other miscellaneous elements.

Internal political changes in a country, for example, change the diplomatic and military capabilities of that country in the international panorama, by changing the distribution of power in the International arena.

At the same time, a structural feature of the international system (the world government, or narcissism produces consequences for the behaviour of the systems of the self-help or self-help system, which, in turn, affects groups and individuals in the States.

However, the relevance of the concept of safety varies accordingly the analysis. This is because security issues refer more directly to political relations of friendship and hostility that accompany the scale of "referential objects" throughout the different levels of analysis.

Laurens Lustgarten and Ian Leigh (1994: 03-35) recognize that, although in axiomatic terms only the safety of individuals from the oral point of view, in empirical terms the most important and comprehensive single in the conditioning of life of an individual is still his 'belonging' to a State national [citizenship].

The insertion of individuals into the family, class social, ethnic, gender, or age group would not have similar impacts on terms of security for their personal existence. Although this is a position at least in relation to social class, it has the advantage of making it clear why security concerns State are not mere derivations or extensions of safety of individuals.

States have primacy as objects of security because their existence is a necessary condition for the realization of any individual or collective value in an international system characterized by the narcissism.

So that public international law identifies national security with state security.

Independent of its differences in relation to any of the four components that define states as a "class of objects" the physical base formed by a population and territory, government institutions, some idea justification that makes those institutions legitimate in the eyes of population and sovereignty, which unfolds in the exclusive exercise of the internal control and control of various flows of interactions with or after sovereign units, all States have as fundamental concerns the continuity of its existence, maintaining its territorial integrity, the survival of its population and independence from other governments.

Direct threat is when the government mobilizes ways of force under its controls against individual targets or groups that are part of the population that should be being protected, which did not infringe any laws or regulations or violated the public order. The coercion was part of the typical trajectory of state construction in modernity in most countries and, even today, when the interests of State are clashing with those of some group or individual, the

rulers and their bureaucracies have the power to try to impose, more or less coercively, his will in the name of public order, morality or national security.

In addition to direct violence on varied scales (from the illegal prison, torture and assassination of regime dissidents to the extent of genocide population), the State also individuals when the criminal justice system and policing are ineffective or arbitrary acts and crimes against the life and property of people can be with impunity or when the rulers implement external and defence policies that greatly increase the divorce between individual security and State security (for example, example, in the case of nuclear dissuasion based on mutual destruction ensure that the population is delivered as a hostage to the stabilize the strategic interaction.

More indirectly still, the struggle between different groups for the control of the state resources that allow governing a population and territory (civil war, revolution or any kind of "multiple sovereignty") threatens the security of individuals and sectors of the population that are not directly involved in the confrontation.

This tension between individual security and state security is a immanent trace of the political order and is manifested with greater or less depending on the nature of the political regime and the integration of each country in the international system.

It must be made clear that the security, insofar as it moves away from strategic studies, tends to research agendas and even try to substitute the discipline of International Relations with the Whole. Whatever the method, the function of the concept of human security has been a research program only to guide the foreign policy of some countries, non-governmental organizations in such agencies and multilateral organizations.

Even as opinion in the political debate (policy advocacy), the approach to human security faces problems of legitimization and dilemma's similar to those already faced by the concept of national security.

First of all, it seems uncritically that without a good thing, a desirable state for any relationships. In secondly over-implementation of the concept allows new rules to be established within the scope of intergovernmental organizations (UN, NATO, etc.) where the interests of the most powerful member countries face the weakest countries by a variety of causes.

Threats involves a large complex of causal factors, diversity of sources As Bair Buzan 1199 1: 142 says), just as the information was perfect and unlimited and not distorted with the inherent complexity of the threats and the consequences of chosen would challenge the actors' ability to discern.

Challenge even more in the case of conflicting interactions in which not only information is available, but the asymmetries and negations of mutual information and deception) are a

component of the interaction itself. All this makes deliberation difficult on security measures and the processes of practices by the "sequencing" actors.

It is precisely to reduce uncertainty and to increase the capacity of national security that there are the armed forces, police and intelligence services. Such organizations are part of the governmental organization for the solution of security problems, but to the extent of safety itself is problematic, such organizations of strength and intelligence are also part of the problem.

In its dual function, informational and coercive, they have their individuality defined by the dilemmas and challenges of National security

Guide to a National Security

In defining the state policy, national security and foreign policy, the starting point is the national interest. If we take as a reference point that only one state is able to give your business a sense of political security, global and comprehensive objectives and national interests are the basic parameters of its overall activity of the state.

However, given the diversity of partial interests that exist within a society, many of them conflicting with each other, the tasks of reconciliation and its final expression as the nation interests is the responsibility of those representing the powers State and have the government function.

This allows identifying the gap between the objectives of state and government. In those, survival, safety and welfare are the immutable aspects of state targets. They are, to give its name, objectives and broader national interests. As a tangible and measurable purposes an exercise of government generally correspond to a specific national project horizons established according to the timing of governance.

Thus, national interests and objectives defining the beginning of the policy of the state – the Great Political – and allows us to separate the permanent objectives – the state – from the strategic – inherent in a government project – in order to confront and make sense of the process of political action in its broadest sense.

Policy decisions are defined behaviours and set goals and courses of action and measures taken to comply. It is clear that the determination of "national interest" cannot respond solely to a single perspective. The vision of the legal, sociological, economic or military analyst is not broad enough to incorporate all the elements of a comprehensive understanding of present reality and future scenarios.

In its implementation or in the evolution of society itself – are generated flows and exchanges of information between internal and external actors involved in social dynamics. These data are quantifiable and qualitative allow access, under a methodical process, an overview of national and international reality and the real determination of objective criteria, that become permanent or strategic objectives.

In this perspective is the balance of national power, the most appropriate approach when analyzing foreign policy and the state ability to take action to achieve their objectives and access to what it calls its interest and security. Security seeks to meet the vital objectives of permanence and survival of the state.

This is important to emphasize this further, as well the national goals and interests and acquire a theoretical significance with a defined methodology for empirical validation.

There is an orthodoxy that divides the power in four fields are the classic political, economic, psychosocial and military. This division should not lead us to consider treatment as an inert object, forgetting that a dynamic relationship exists in human society.

The 'fields of power' are frameworks that encompass activities consistent with each other by nature and are useful for the analysis of these in relation to the exercise of power and the genesis of it. In terms of national development uses, the National Power as a view for improving material and spiritual culture of society in terms of national security must be employed as a strategic tool, e.g. in order to overcome, neutralize or reduce the antagonisms that are filed with obtaining and maintaining permanent national objectives.

The usual method is to diagnose the political reality in the broad sense that allows you to include the set of social relations within the state, political and strategic goals, according to the national interest, strategic inventory and strategic diagnosis, interpreting international stage according to the objectives and capabilities of the various instruments available to the state for external and internal action, and, finally, the action plan.

The coding of information into knowledge flows "useful and vital to the survival and security of the nation," representing the efficient implementation of the instruments of power of a State, in time and more favourable circumstances achieving their goals.

National reality is the source of conception of foreign policy and whose needs must be satisfied that through their action in different areas in which the state interacts with the outside. From the reality when the planning process begins to take on foreign policy objective and is, in turn, a mechanism that provides guidance about what the national needs, from which the foreign policy objectives are paths is obvious that not only govern define the statistics and determine the national interest.

Others factors affecting the survival of the state, territorial integrity and full autonomy of decisions of domestic and foreign policy are the ultimate goal of any process of foreign policy. The national interest is more than the standard by which situational factors are considered relevant and suggest certain behaviour.

It is also the ultimate yardstick used to measure the success or failure of the state. The concept of interest is both at the starting point and purpose of the foreign policy process, so the entire sequence of events acquires a peculiarly circular.

Under the American view, national interest is irreducible. Henry Kissinger argues that every State must try to reconcile what he considers fair with what he considers possible. What is considered fair depends on the internal structure of their state. They may depend on its resources, geographic position and determination and resources, determination and internal structure of other states. In

these terms, the nature of national power is concatenated to the interests and objectives. For that reason alone the State is capable of exercising a responsible and national security policy as it is also designing and implementing foreign policy, which is not detached from the general policy of the state.

The components of national power of the state, qualitative and quantitative factors of economic, political, social and military power are needed to interpret the same state as a dynamic social relationship, which necessarily interacts with all facets of social behaviour.

The combination of these optical multidisciplinary appreciate the history and present of nations, as part of social and institutional contents of the country, under the deposit of state powers in the government figure, defines the policies to follow. This statement is of particular importance as it cannot be separated from the external to internal power, and in many ways, the way state acts have to do with the image it has of himself, that reaching out and that others have of it.

Schematically, the assertion that the national and international power means "... The power or ability of the subjects of international society to impose its own will on others, based on the preparation of its population, as well as the quantity, quality and use of resources at their disposal, in determining the degree of organization and development they have attained in all spheres: political, economic, legal, social, cultural, scientific, technical, military, etc.. as well as the objectives of its foreign policy, and supported by the ability of its armed forces and the complexity of their arms. Therefore, power is a complex global power that determines the specific weight of each actors of contemporary international society.

The ability and willingness to exercise (power) reflects the degree of cohesion and direction in national policy and have given concrete expression in the international arena. In this perspective is the conceptualization of Raymond Aron, external action is not only diplomacy, in the narrowest sense of the term... but also influences or pressures, voluntary or otherwise, brought by the country on other countries, both because of what it is, and because of what he does, and both its multinational companies as their diplomats.

National Power reflects possibilities and limitations in it. National Power flows from state power, the exercise of delegated to the nation state, which has the power to establish and implement the political-legal process.

Thus, the State, such as monopolizing the use of force, avoiding anarchic violence between individuals and gives the government the means to enforce the institutional comprehensiveness of the National Power is the result of the agglutination of all means available to the nation: political, economic, social (psychosocial) and military.

National Power serves the domestic and foreign policy externally is surety instrument of sovereignty, aimed to conquer and preserve national objectives relating to international relations.

These are called the sovereign independence of states, the absence of a higher power, and the detachment from all external brake, which attaches to relations between states his peculiar sense of anarchy.

There are three powerful imperatives: the prestige, fear and interest, as it is natural that the weak law is dominated by the strong.

Power has formed an indissoluble part of the study of relations between states and ways in which power became the main catalyst for the evolution in the forms of political organization.

Without explaining the power it cannot be explained the historical evolution of the social community clustered in the political, from the primitive commune to the supranational schemes today. Hence the use of power in relations between states was analyzed also as a synonym of “power politics”, generally from the perspective of “realpolitik”.

The power in international relations is the ability of a nation to use its tangible and intangible resources, so that they can affect the behaviour of other nations.

According to a more specialized, the politics of power are a system of international relations in which groups regard themselves, as the ultimate goals, employ at least vital purposes, the most effective means at their disposal and are measured according to their weight in case of conflict.

Power politics generally are interpreted from the perspective of interstate and as sources of power have their own internal conditions of which becomes its capacity. Hence, National Power, Foreign Policy and Political Power as communicating vessels are the sources of power and capacity.

Thus we can summarize these power politics as a means to achieve the purposes of the nation, and also view internal policies (or domestic), and in foreign policy, because in all these are seeking for power.

The effectiveness of power and significance of their policies is measuring and valuing power, played by objective basis for defining and quantifying multidisciplinary sectors, e.g. – In the effective and efficient use of national power. While power is a relative term, the capabilities are not.

Often it is stated that the power of a nation is simply the sum total of their abilities but always entails power capabilities, is also related to other dimensions. It is important that, while the skills can be delimited objectively, the power must be assessed in every case in terms of psychological and subtle relationship.

In the same vein, Kissinger said that “most of history has shown a synthesis of military, political and economic, which has generally proven to be symmetrical. The sheer will is not enough to the satisfaction of interests; you need the ability to do so.

In this summarizes the genesis of power: to prioritize the satisfaction of the interests that man needs to use available means and resources and ensure that they can impose their will, so you can secure control over the obstructions to the achievement of their interests reflecting the possibilities and limitations of National Power.

So does the ability by the end of this century and millennium, a financial institution charged with the uncompromising defence of the principles of neoliberal and monetarism emerged from the Chicago school in the eighties, the World Bank, the state role revalues and emphasizes the full use of state capacities, under the sign of efficiency.

An effective state is essential to have the goods and services – and the rules and institutions-that allow markets to flourish and people to lead healthier and happier life. Experience taught us that the state is central to the process of economic and social development, but not as a direct provider of growth but as a partner, catalyst and initiator of this process. The world is changing and with it also changes our ideas about the role of government in economic and social development.

Intelligence Services

Intelligence services are government agencies responsible for the collection, analysis and disclosure of information considered relevant to the decision-making process and the implementation of public policies in the areas of foreign policy, national defence, and public order.

These government agencies are also known as secret services or information services. Although the use of spies and specialized informants goes back to antiquity in areas as dispersed as Chennai, the Near East, and the Roman Empire, intelligence activity has acquired a new operational scale as a social, professional and permanent occupation of the modern state in Europe. Even then, intelligence services, as we know them today, really only began to institutionalize in the twentieth century.

After the end of the Cold War, in many countries the necessity and role of these services was debated, which might indicate that their growing institutional weight was in fact only a passing phenomenon, a product of the two world wars and the Cold War itself.

During the first half of the 1990s, the services of intelligence had in fact had their budgets reduced significantly while the new international context became more volatile and, as a result, the demands for information became more demanding and diversified.

On the other way, the emergence and rapid growth of new information and communication technologies (ICTs) enabled private companies to offer information on insurance issues on a global scale, competing in many areas with the services of intelligence for the attention and government resources. The response of the intelligence services to these challenges initially tended to be reactive, adapting to the new budgets and to the new international scene.

However, as the 21st century commenced and intelligence services continued to be a stable part of the government apparatus of the countries, the typical response to the challenges of the new international reality tended to shift to a much more " IOIU profile "on the efficiency and effectiveness of intelligence services in fulfilling their goals.

In the context more direct competition with other information providers, more scarce resources and a changing international situation, the search for agility would correspond to a strategy based on three integrated axes:

1) **Speed:** the processes of collection, analysis and dissemination

2) **Capacity:** how raw data collection and production technologies have vastly exceeded the capacity for processing, production and retrieval of "finished" intelligence. An increase in capacity in these areas becomes crucial for intelligence organizations to be able to add higher-value-added inputs to the decision-making processes of the national security area.

3) **Flexibility:** to the extent that crises and external political issues appear and disappear without much notice overlapping it, the increasingly demanding agenda of governors, the cost and benefit relationships of resources invested in intelligence organizations involve increasing pressures for greater flexibility and also for greater integration between the various agencies.

Although Frederick Martin's Freeman deals extensively with the several technological difficulties and organizational culture for the realization of this concept of "agility" in North American intelligence agencies, problems arising from the especially characteristics and the operation of intelligence activities are largely underestimated.

This, in general, is a problem little explored by the specialized literature. Acronyms such as CIA, KGB, MOSSAD are relatively familiar to the public, but the average knowledge about their activities and structures is restricted to some picturesque facts or images distorted by the imagination and fictional literature.

In this sense, is a persistent trajectory of the intelligence services and just their relative opacity, the secret mantle that surrounds their activities.

As the transparency of governmental acts and one of the most valued requirements of the political practice contemporary (and the main unfulfilled promise of democracy), it is not surprising that the mere existence of intelligence services generates detachment and insecurity in the citizens that question themselves who have such organizations.

The negative view that the citizens tend to have of the services of intelligence of their own poses makes transparency a great challenge in the process of the use of these activities.

To introduce the theme, let us return to the text of Italo Calvino. According to Calvino, visibility as a literary value involves not only the ability to see the reality of the world and tradition, but in originality and invention, the capacity for abstract imagination is absent and decisive and will be negatively affected by the saturation of pre-fabricated images.

This phenomenon would seem to be imperative, which Calvino calls the "pedagogy of imitation". an education that enables us to express verbally and through writing the polymorphic visions obtained through the eyes and the soul.

Although the idea of visibility in Calvino is incomprehensible in relation to the idea of three dimensions as a dilemma of nationalisation, it is suggestive because it evokes the kind of

ambiguity and challenge that must be dealt with in approaching the phenomenon of the transparency of governmental acts.

Ambiguity that is expressed including, for the fact that transparency can mean both visibility and invisibility.

For example, non-transparent visual transparency used to highlight the invisible ownership of interfaces, which ensures that users can use resources and solve problems without having to go through all the steps and interoperable operations performed by the system. In general, the so-called state activities (where information-gathering activities are included for decision-making) were, in this case, transparent to the citizens, who would look through them to visualize and control the acts of the rulers in relation to the ends considered desirable by the political community.

However, bureaucratic inefficiency, and corruption make the administrative environment opaque and its own governmental acts more conducive to the emergence of a republican principle it's democratic associated with it does not value the invisibility of the system, but rather it seeks the capacity - on the part of the citizen - to visualize and judge for itself what governments are doing in the various spheres of political action.

This ability to make use of his own tenderness is in the sense that it brings transparency and brings it closer to educated visibility, as Calvino expresses fearlessly.

For David Luban (1996: 154-198), the transparency of governmental acts, norms, and policies is a necessary condition for the development of the popular struggle that underpins the democratic institutions and legitimizes the governments' desires to obtain collaboration and obedience from governed.

The principle of publicity is a moral proposition and also a principle of institutional design. No governmental agency or area of government argues, to remain consistent with the principle of third party should be built according to operating lines that depended on the secret to its effectiveness and efficiency.

However, intelligence services are just organizations that depend on secrecy about their methods of inquiry and their sources of information to operate effectively. To the extent that the process of institutionalizing this type of organization implies not only an effort to become stable, but also a quest for recognition and value in the eyes of citizens, which depends on transparency.

In truth, as David Luban himself says, government secrecy and intelligence activities are compatible with the pre-eminence of the party only when the justification for its existence can be made, itself, in public. In these terms, the Luban's proposal provides an interesting starting point for the analysis of the complexities, tensions and conditions of possibility associated with transparency as a non-institutional requirement.

Although the two normative present themselves as challenges in the trajectory of any organization, rule or procedure and, in the limit, they constitute a double dilemma of institutionalization. It is not a matter here of reiterating the technocratic argument about the existence of a trade-off mechanism between agility and transparency, through which gains in one form or another would be at the expense of the other.

The authoritarian implications of such an argument are very clear in suggesting, for example, that government efficiency would largely depend on secrecy and bureaucratic insulation. Or, from the angle, that institutional gain in this respect necessarily limits the ability of the organizations.

While it is reasonable to suppose that the secret of a functional requirement is less or less relevant to the effectiveness and efficiency of certain government actions, this does not eliminate the problem of public justification (transparency) about the very need for those secrets.

On the other hand, although it can be argued that legitimacy is one of the conditions that ensure the efficiency and effectiveness (agility) of government action, it is equally wrong to assume that all problems of agility could be re-established through institutional gains in transparency.

"There are a number of ongoing international research initiatives currently underway, both in the area of intelligence studies of the Intellectual Property Association (IISAI), and in the field of intelligence. British SWD Group on Intelligence, the Canadian Association for Security and Intelligence Studies (CASIS), the Consortium for the SWD of Intelligence (Georgetown University), the Harvard's Intelligence and Policy Program (John Kennedy School of Government) History Group (IIHG, headquartered in Germany) to name but a few.

In general, we can situate intelligence studies as a material in the field of Strategic Studies, which can be defined as the field of studies that have the main objective of analyzing the phenomena associated with the use of the force to compel.

1 -Intelligence: Operational Dynamics

"Intelligence is concerned with that component of the struggle between nations that deals with information." Intelligence seeks to learn all about the world. But intelligence can never forget that attainment of the truth: involves a struggle with human enemy who is fighting back and that truth is not the goal but rather only means to victory. " Abraham Shulsky, *Silent Warfare*, 1992. p. 197.

There are two main uses of the term intelligence outside the scope of the cognitive sciences. **A broad definition says intelligence and all information collected, organized or analyzed to meet the demands of any decision maker.** For intelligence, intelligence and a

specific layer of aggregation and non-analytical treatment in an informational pyramidal, formed on the basis of raw data and, in the vertex, reflexive knowledge.

The increasing technological sophistication of information systems that support decision-making has made the use of intelligence more common to designate this function of its size, be it in the routine of the government, in the middle enterprise or even in social organizations. In this sense, intelligence, and even the knowledge or information analyzed.

It is certainly possible to theorize about the nature of information and the impact of total flows of information on the economy, the state and social life in a general way. However, the intelligibility of this work refers to more limited sets of information structured information flows. In this case, a narrow definition states that intelligence and the collection of information without consent, cooperation, or even knowledge on the part of the targets of the action. In this restricted sense, intelligence is the same as secret or secret information.

To ignore the narrow definition would imply losing sight of what makes this problematic activity ultimately. In the real world, however, intelligence service activities are broader than espionage and are more restricted than providing information in general on any issues relevant to government decision-making. This poses a very concrete difficulty for a precise action of the activity of intelligence which pervades it differs from the excessively broad notion of information and the excessively narrow notion of espionage.

While the first statement highlights the special means used to collect information without the cooperation and / or the knowledge of an advisor, this second dimension and analysis basically says that intelligence differs from mere informing by its explanatory and / or predictive capacity. The combination of these two faces or dimensions are the basis of the concept of intelligence is an organization of the work process involved.

This approach has been more precisely described by Michael Herman as a trenching process, separate from a collecting and specialized collection system, and sources of information (single-sources collection), followed by a stage of analysis of the information obtained from the various single sources and other non- structured flows.

The persistent association between intelligence and conflict is strong precisely because the two dimmers of the concept are non-dissociable in the praxis of the organizations in charge of providing this type of information and knowledge.

Both the practical difficulties and the criteria for a differentiation of the activity that supports this association between intelligence and conflict can be demonstrated through two epistemic delimitations, each of them based on one of the faces of the concept.

In relation to the analytical description of the concept, the difference between the analyzes and estimates elaborated in the field of intelligence activities and any other analyzes of

governmental technical advisory bodies is for the purposes of intelligence analysis: to increase the level of awareness of adversaries and to problems affecting national and state security (situational awareness).

They differ from geography and statistical institutes or from centres of economic research, intelligence and services geared to the understanding of economic relations and therefore most of their targets and problems are mainly international and "difficult".

Intelligence deals with the "other" study and seeks to elucidate situations in which relevant information is potentially manipulated or hidden, where there is an organized effort on the part of an adversary to misinform, to render opaque the understanding and to deny with effect.

The security intelligence services have many purely economic objectives, but even these share the condition of others in the eyes of the constitutional party and the constituted political order.

The argument applies even to the study of facts and problems not directly related to a specific actor. Not all national and international issues that are potentially relevant to a government are adequately addressed by intelligence services. Even though the list of issues on which agencies need to inform their users is growing, ranging from cultural aspects of societies to details of technologies.

Even though the list of issues on which agencies need to inform their users is growing, ranging from cultural aspects of societies, to details of technologies for use, new items should be incorporated the work agenda of intelligence agencies only when they have the ability to "add value" in areas that are not their specialty, but where their sources and methods are deemed necessary by civilian and military users.

Finally, the more open the sources of information and the less conflicting the issues and situations, the more intelligence analyzes will contribute to the decision-making process of the mind.

This is a criterion that emphasizes the value of a narrow definition of irrelevancy. The frontier of analytical work in intelligence needs to be broken in relation to some connection with the detachment of the analyzed to the processes of governmental decision in international politics, national defence and provision of public order.

Regarding the operative meaning of the concept, the difference between the collection of information for purposes of intelligence production and / or after government operations involving the systematic collection of information on actors and problems relevant to national security and more nebulous, impossible to trace, two typical situations in which this difference can be seen are the diplomatic relations between states and military operations.

Normally, countries maintain diplomatic relations and each sovereign state allows the formal representations of the other States in their territories to send reports to their governments and countries.

While intelligence officials have been open to discussion, it is quite possible that certain private sources of the ambassadors overlap the sources of the spies. In contrast, the differences between an activity and a relatively small number of activities, especially with respect to the degree of fragility of diplomatic sources or information overloads in relation to security measures of the targets.

Most of the sources of a diplomat are pretentious and do not cease informational illusion when the government of the host country increases its security procedures, which tends to occur with the sources of intelligence officers.

It is sufficient it to say that diplomats, military attachés or international experts suspected of espionage are decelerated persona non grata, expelled from the country of lodging and returned to their countries of origin on the basis of the Vienna Diplomatic Relations Conference.

Efforts to obtain information through diplomatic channels and through intelligence operations are re-evaluated as different by the actors involved, mainly on the basis of the different means used.

In the case of military operations, it may be more appropriate to speak of a continuum of combat intelligence and intelligence. Even in combat situations, however, certain specificities have led to intelligence activity.

The most obvious is the degree of control that intelligence organizations have over each type of information flow. In the case of combat information, this will normally be the data obtained as a function of the direct contact of the troops with the enemy - and which are used immediately for operational alert or for the decision on immediate action.

Although some of these data can later be integrated into the information flows that feed into the production and dissemination stage of intelligence reports, these data are controlled by the (rather than the intelligible) functions of the command structures of the forces. The combat information remains an activity distinct from intelligence activities,

In spite of this pragmatic criterion on who controls the means of collection and the resulting informational flows, it is not always easy to apply the criterion. In the Persian Gulf War of 1991, the United Nations military reconnaissance was supported by North American satellites and analysts controlled by the CIA and Pentagon intelligence agencies, as well as counting on intelligence operations .

Both the intelligence work and the battle information management depended heavily on the airborne command and control systems such as the AWACS (Airborne Warning and

Control Systems) and JSTARS (Joint Swerve Target Attack Radar Systems), subordinated to the allied command in the theatre. In other words, with a greater integration of joint military operations, operational control of specific intelligence resources and combat information can change the sphere of command depending on the needs, as in the case of the military units of tactical intelligence collection eventually used by the artillery or satellites transmitting signals and / or decoding processed directly on the command of unit commanders in the operating theatre.

Timelines and the growing sophistication of resources available for the generation of combat information (targeting, alerting, and electronic warfare operations) also contribute to the creation of new shadow areas between intelligence and operational information combat, especially between the areas of intelligence of operations of support of electronic warfare. In particular, when it comes to localize, it identifies and produces countermeasures in the electronic radar and warning systems, and it is difficult to know where one thing starts and another.

Intelligence cycle

The uncommon descriptions of the intelligence cycle are able to detect up to ten steps or main steps that characterize the activity, namely:

- 1) **Informational requirements.**
- 2) **Planning.**
- 3) **Management of the technical means of collection.**
- 4) **Collection from singular sources.**
- 5) **Processing.**
- 6) **Analysis of the information obtained from various sources.**
- 7) **Producing reports, reports and studies.**
- 8) **Dissemination of products.**
- 9) **Consumption by users.**
- 10) **Evaluation feedback.**

The idea of intelligence culture must be seen as a metaphor. a simplified model that does not exactly correspond to any truly existing intelligence system.

On the other hand, this lack of descriptive perception is not what matters, since the characterization of activities is intelligence, while a complex and directional process of work is important so that qualitative changes can be distinguished that the information suffers

during a cycle uninterrupted and interrelated work. The main contribution of the idea of the intelligence cycle is precisely to help understand this

As the activity of intelligence and itself a subordinate function of the processes of formulas, decision and implementation of foreign policy, defence and public security, we can also think of the cycle of intelligence as a sub-set of activities of the so-called "public policy cycle": a cycle made by the emergence of problems (issues, the establishment of an agenda, the formation of policies and lines of action, the processes of decision-making, implementation and evaluation. "In this sense, information that intelligence services collect and analyze should be determined by their needs and priorities usuries.

Ideally, decision makers, whether elected politicians, ministers, senior civilian bureaucrats, military commanders or police chiefs, identify gaps and information needs, set priorities, and pass them on to intelligence leaders. These, in turn, transform those needs perceived by users into information requirements for the responsible sectors through collection and analysis.

Given that even the resources of the countries are scarce, those responsible for the various collection disciplines need to plan the use of the technical means and human resources available to produce the maximum possible synergy and meet the demands of the policymakers. The management of the technical means of collection, depending on the platforms used (airplanes, fixed intercepting units, satellites, etc.), and a specialized activity and highly complex.

It is important to point out this difference between the general planning of information collection and the management of technical means, Michael Herman (1996: 283-304) and Mark Lowenthal (2000: 40-521) point out in most situations policymakers do not have the time or the clarity to specify the kinds of information they need or will need for what In these cases, the lists of demands tend to be geriatrics (for example, a request for reports on the "situation" in Colombia), or they are formulated without the intelligence officers having a precise idea about the purpose of the information in the general context of the challenges faced by the government (for example, a requirement on the performance of troop transport helicopters of a particular Russian manufacturer, without revealing the area of intelligence that that report is necessary for decision-making regarding the alternatives of action in relation to the conflict in Colombia.)

That is, the uncertain nature of politics and the pressure of patterns of thought derived from experience s more or less recent trends tend to make user "requirements" somewhat more structured than the initial assumption of the model. These formal requirements legitimize and provide an authorization for agencies to mobilize their means for the production of intelligence on a particular problem or target, but rather is not the only factor determining the intelligence activity cycle.

It will, therefore, fit into the areas of intelligence and use a set of organizational and analytical tools to complete, detail, and address those demands, putting them into more effective informational requirements. While it is imperative that intelligence agencies act on this specification to avoid a "failure of requirements" that would jeopardize the entire cycle, there is a clear risk of intrusion and autonomy of agencies in areas that would be the prerogative of the host authorities.

Even taking into account such risks, Michael Herman (1996: 288) maintains that a proactive role of agencies is preferable and compatible with the maintenance of a high level of responsiveness, provided that it is accompanied by procedures for the systematic evaluation of the satisfaction of users with the intelligence products received and external control mechanisms.

According to Lisa Krizan (1999: 13-201), even with the correct use of tools aimed at identifying the needs of users (eg taxonomy of problems, lists of questionnaires and timing and scope), and bear in mind that the information flows associated with the requirements present complexity. In addition to structured requirements to meet the needs of the various types of end users, which are communicated to collection agencies by the national and also consider that many of these users communicate their needs directly to collection agencies.

And that individual critique analysts call for not only information on the current requirements of users, but also a wider range of information needed for database design and / or a wider understanding of targets and problems on which analysts are working. Finally, it should be noted that collecting agencies also work from opportunities created by eventual security failures of the adversaries.

Therefore, procedural, cognitive, and even resource scarcities show that the so-called intelligence activity cycle depends much more on the initiative of the intelligence agencies themselves than the metaphor of a cycle initiated and directed by formal user requirements would indicate the first view.

Collection and Processing

The specialized collection activities absorb between 80% and 90% of government investments in the area of intelligence in the countries

Most of these resources are dedicated to the platforms, sensors and technological systems for collecting and processing information, especially the satellites in the case of the United States, Russia, China, France and other few countries that operate such fleets. The volume of raw data and primary information collected is much larger than the reports actually received by the final users. According to an estimate of the 1980s, only 10% of the information collected would come out of the walls of intelligence systems.

The means of collecting and the typical sources of information define disciplines which are specialized in intelligence, which the international literature refers to by means of acronyms derived from the use of the United States in the: humint language for information obtained from human sources, sigint for the information obtained from the interception and decoding of communications and electromagnetic signals for the information obtained from the production and interpretation of photographic and multispectral images, masint (measurement and signature intelligence) for the information obtained from the onset of other types of emanation, such as the characteristic and individualized signals of vehicles, platforms and weapons systems.

In addition to these disciplines, involving both natural and ostensible sources, when collecting information exclusively from public, private, or electronic sources, this collecting activity is then called osint open sources intelligence. See briefly each of these disciplines.

Humint

The English word for this discipline (humint) is typically American euphemism, embedded in international jargon because it avoids the use of the espionage term, much heavier from a legal and political point of view. The acronym also is used to indicate that the intelligence obtained from human is far from being summarized as archetypes of espionage.

And you need to basically differentiate between two kinds of tiers in this area: the intelligence officers, that are those career workers who will work for an intelligence service and are accountable for the information - gathering operations, and their sources, some of which are agents. The current civil and military humint organizations are responsible for but are also affected by a variety of non-natural sources. Base non the pyramid de humint are the less glamorous sources, with access to the less sensitive information and insulated value.

Secure services maintain systematic services in ideal interviews; with persons who have access to countries or areas that are "difficult" or difficult, for which information from travellers and occasional travellers, academic experts, business contacts or even refugees and individuals from oppressed communities may be useful.

In war situations an important source of information is the populations of occupied areas and the prisoners of war IPOWs interrogated by the intelligence units of the armed forces.

In neither of these cases are sources of formal intelligence service and such programs tend to be conducted by other officers of the organization, not the responsible by the espionage operations themselves.

However, no. measured in which it passes from the relatively passive exploitation of what the sources already know for a more active attempt to solicit certain types of information (Tasking, this means a certain progression upward in the pyramid.) In this intermediate layer

of sources are ad hoc informants, political exiles, opposition parties, etc. The degree of clandestinely in contacts with this type of source can vary, ranging from the formal approach to the provision of specific information, to the manipulation of sources and the obtaining of information without the target having even conscience of the relationship with an intelligence agency, often disguised as a newspaper or commercial contact.

On top of secret sources that regularly transmit information that may not be numerous, but tend to be better value-added and high-sensitivity. These regular agents, who are aware that they are spying on their own government or organization and provide more or less vital information to national security for foreign intelligence services, may be both agents recruited by intelligence officers and people who would volunteer to perform such. In general, volatile agents are viewed with much disagreement by foreign intelligence services as they may be part of the operations of the security services of the target country and have as their mission misinforming, or infiltrating the intelligence service that it accepts.

On the other hand, excessive suspicion may prevent access to a well-placed source. And in the past, the goal by which someone corrodes to spy on an adversary is rather varied and changes over.

From the point of view of the intelligence services responsible for directing the programs and recruited agents, it is necessary to differentiate two basic categories of intelligence officers from abroad: those operating with official coverage and the others.

Official coverage refers to the integration of intelligence officers into the diplomatic corps of the embassy or consulate, disguised as a cultural attaché, political adviser, technician, assistant to the military attaché, representative of the ministry of agriculture, secretary or any other government official an offense to be in that country, and also to grant diplomatic immunity in case of detection of their true activities, since international law requires that such officers be declared *personae non grata* and expelled from the country.

In addition, the authorities of the country being spied on and the security provided by the embassy and consulates, so that the intelligence officers can maintain their archives and comprise themselves with the headquarters of their service, country of origin.

The most senior officer conducting intelligence operations in a foreign country heads the "station" (in the North-American jargon, or the "rezidentura", in the Russian jargon) of his intelligence service, official coverage facilitates the work of counter-espionage surveillance teams of the target population, limits the types of persons with whom intelligence officers may contact without raising suspicion, and in extreme cases where diplomatic relations are interrupted, this deconstructs the work of collecting information.

The use of officers without "official" coverage (NO in the jargon, or "illegals" in the jargon) are located in the greater flexibility and efficiency of operations. Setting up coverage scenarios that can relate to a variety of social and professional strata representatives of

foreigners, foreigners of a third nationality, ecologists, members of the clergy, doctors, etc.), intelligence services amplify the range of possible targets for the recruitment of agents and informants, and make work difficult of counter-espionage surveillance.

On the other hand, this may limit contact with the official world, expose the service frameworks to a much higher level, not to mention that nongovernmental coverage requires a much longer maturation and training period, as well as logistical requirements and communications are much more complex.

In general, intelligence obtained from human sources (humint) is not only the oldest and cheapest way of obtaining secret information, but it is also the most problematic.

Management problems range from the enormous pressure on staff recruited, no matter what kind of promotion has led them to spy, to the difficulties associated with controlling the credibility of the source and the reliability and accuracy of information, in addition to the risks represented counter-espionage operations of adversaries which attempt to neutralize the agents or then corrode them as double agents, there is a risk always present in the sources themselves, tempted to fill certain informational data with information made in paper mills.

In addition to security issues and difficulties in controlling the quality of the information obtained, other operational features of the humint area are derived from the long processes of identification and recruitment of agents, from restricted committees between agents and their controllers, and of all the cognitive and intellectual systems inherent in direct human obedience.

Despite these limitations, it is irreplaceable as a source of information. Especially when it comes to discovering the real intentions of an actor, intercepted messages (sigint) or photographs (imint) are insufficient evidences.

Documents and oral explanations present, at least potentially, a degree of comprehensiveness that the other disciplines of collection have not yet been able to obtain.

Spying is often indispensable for an effective exploitation of other sources of information, as the production of copies of coded books and ciphered materials has always helped the cryptology area of the sigint organization.

Based on this flexible and specialized organizational track record of Michael Herman (1996: 65-66), there is a tendency for organizations specialized in humint to function as multi-purpose organizations, ranging from actual espionage to the pioneering development of new forms of collection of information through technical means.

Sigint

The second ancient discipline of collecting information is known as intelligence of signals or **sigint** (signals intelligence).

Historically, sigint has originated from interception, decoding, translation and analysis of samples by a third party, besides the issuer and the intended offender. With the increasing use of communications written for military or diplomatic purposes in the modern world, the disciplines of cryptography (use of codes and figures to ensure the inviolability of messages) and cryptology [deciphering and / or decoding of intercepted messages] Intelligence is divided into two compliant fields, called **comint** (communications intelligence) and **elint** (electronics intelligence).

Intelligence of communications, or comint, is obtained through the interception, processing and pre-analysis of the communications of governments, organizations and individuals, except for the monitoring of public radio and television broadcasting, which fall in the area of osint. In addition to the access to the content of the transmitted messages, one can also monitor the traffic patterns of messages between different points (traffic analysis) and also through direction-finding (DF) traffic and localization of transmissions are an integral part of the comint discipline.

In turn, electronic intelligence, or elint is obtained through the interception, processing and pre-analysis of non-communicative electromagnetic signals emitted with civilian equipment, with the exception of the **ernissces** resulting from nuclear explosions, which fall in the area of masint specialization.

The first targets of the elint operations were the radars of the air defence systems. With the development of the missiles and the proliferation of the use of electronic equipment throughout the Cold War, they will have other priority targets for various types of radar, mainly operating systems (target acquisition, browsers, mobile phones, etc.) and command, control, communication, and intelligence systems.

According to Jeffrey Richelson (1999: 182-1851), the ease with which communications and / or electronic signals can be intercepted and interpreted depends on three factors: the method of transmission, the frequencies employed, and the use of defensive measures, especially encryption.

The most secure way of transmitting important and non-communicable information, but "radio silence" policies and emission reduction programs run counter to the needs of communication of complex organizations and human failures, or less inevitable.

At a less demanding level, large amounts through land and sea cables, especially fiber optic cables, are also safer. The interception of this type of traffic depends on the physical access to the tapping cables, a low productivity and costly operation, which is extremely difficult in the case of fiber optic cables. In the other hand, since the advent of the wireless telegraph, the transmission of electromagnetic signals transmitted by air has made it physically simpler

to collect information, raising the potential for the importance of safety measures and the need to. According to these measures, sigint organizations now face not only sophisticated, commercially available cryptographic and scrambling features but also a variety of technologies, technologies, and communications systems for military use that challenge interception and decoding.

Throughout the INTELSAT International Telecommunications Satellite Organization satellites network, more than two-thirds of all international telephone traffic passes, virtually all international trunks of television signals, as well as most digitized faxes and e-mail, video and teleconferences.

Given the disparity of media in the area of intelligence gathering, the capacity such as the United States and, to a lesser extent, the other Western European countries of NATO, Russia and China, tends to be much higher than the capacity of other governments or companies guarantee the safety of their COMSEC commissions, even with the cheapening of new ITIC information and communication technologies.

As was widely publicized during European Parliament investigations in 1999 on the so-called Echelon, only the United States network of ten fixed stations monitoring global satellite communications intercepted a monthly volume about the number of messages, including Internet, telephony, cell telephony, bank transfers, fax services, and other signals.

In fact, considering all other systems and platforms combined the interception capacity of the United States and much larger than that. According to Matthew Aid (2000: 17-21, as early as 1995 the central agency of the US INSA) was able to intercept a volume of signals equivalent to all the information volume of the Library of Congress (1 quadrillion bits) every three hours of operation of platforms and sensors in the whole world.

The major problem of the **sigint** area would be the lack of ability to process such huge volumes of intercepts. Existing estimates for the United States point to a re-examination of one input system for each reporting. And the processing of the volume of intercepted traffic are no less important than the low yield of useful material in re-reading of the total volume.

While the NSA was able to process 20 percent of everything that was intercepted in the 1980s, since the explosion of new technologies in 1990, the agency would not be able to process more than 1% of all intercepted material.

Processing, decoding, translation, storage, retrieval, and dissemination of systems are as important as or more decisive for investment in research and development, such as technologies, sensors and collection platforms.

Especially in the North American and Russian cases, in addition to large terrestrial traffic interception stations, listening posts are also used in foreign capitals (for interception of official short-distance communications, including cellular phones), operation centers and

from mobile aircraft and drones (UAVs) to ships and submarines equipped with sensors and personnel specialized in the collection of sigint. Since the 1960s, however, no platform has been so important and how much the satellites of electronic surveillance and interception of communications. These large "ears" or "aspirators" began to be placed in space orbit even before the imaging satellites and constitute the majority of the fleets of spy satellites.⁶¹ Basically, they existed currently main types of satellites of sigint.

Imint

Although visual evidence has been important for military operations long before the invention of photography, the emergence of the imint area as a specialized discipline of information gathering and subsequent use of the military aircraft for reconnaissance and surveillance during and after the two wars of the twentieth century.

Photographic images, televised images and other types of visual evidence are also obtained by intelligence officers, reconnaissance patrols, and surveillance teams on land and at sea. However, the development of imint as a specialized discipline for the collection of information was mainly based on the use of photographic cameras and aerial-space platforms.

According to William Odom (1997: 791 and Jeffrey Richelson 1999: 1501), the historical roots of collection and use of visual evidence for the production of intelligence go back to the drawings made by military officers in reconnaissance missions, terrain, panoramas, fortifications, ports, etc.) have historically been part of the necessities for the planning and execution of military operations.

However, current aerospace platforms for the collection of visual evidence have had recent roots in the company of aerostiers (balloons) organized by the French after RevCuvec of 1789. or in similar attempts to use haloes for reconnaissance missions by troops of the United States during the American Civil War of 1861-1865, and later in the late 19th century by the British and German armies.

As of World War I, photographic work began to be installed on sent airplanes in reconnaissance missions, the greater reach of the aircraft at the time of the Second War allowed a bold use of air reconnaissance flights covered by enemy territory.

By using ever-changing chambers, films, and lenses for vertical and oblique photos, mounted on pocketable aircrafts and adapted bombers, an intense and systematic exploration of visual evidence in the production of in- of the Cold War after 1945, the nature of the territory of the Soviet Union and the lack of access to other sources of information led the United States to intensify high-altitude aerial photographs over Soviet territory and in its more immediate periphery the development of systems and specialized platforms in intelligence collection has since added a specific layer to the competitive and conflictive policy that would mark the Cold War between the United States and the Soviet Union.

The diplomatic-military revenues derived from the violation of the air space of nations and represented by the enhancement of defensive countermeasures for detecting and intercepting spy planes, have led most countries to a relatively restricted use of flights to destinations of reconnaissance.

Until 1960, however, the United States used several types of aircraft for reconnaissance missions over the Soviet territory, especially because for some time U-2s, high-speed, range and altitude were unreachable by Soviet interceptors, although these airplanes were and still are used in a variety of places and missions, the episode of the overthrow of one of them by Soviet planes in 1960 was the milestone of a new stage in the development of the area of imint.

At the beginning of the decade, the United States, and soon afterwards the Soviet Union, succeeded for the first time in orbiting spy satellites capable of flying over adversarial territories and photographing targets on an impermissible scale with the systems then available.

Despite the high degree of secrecy surrounding military satellite image programs, between 1967 (when the Outer Space Treaty was signed) and 1992 (when the Open Skies Treaty was signed), or the restricted club of the powers that have collection capacities of imint from space platforms more or less tacitly accepted the inevitability of these over flights.

With much more limited resources than those available to the United States and Russia, these countries include (or will include in the next years) France, China, India, China, Israel, South Africa, Canada, North Korea, and Taiwan. Over the last decade, some of the technical and political advantages of satellites have even affected the countries that have their own fleets, as far as they are concerned in which commercially sold images with better resolution will be made available.

In general, these developments have contributed for the discipline of imint every time central to the operational dynamics of the collection activities of intelligence.

In the first place, image satellites can cross the territory of a country without being considered by international law as a violation of the national airspace.

Basically, image satellites move in relatively low altitude circular orbits than sigint satellites (eg the North American imaging satellites known as KH-11 advanced operate with 241km of perigee and 965km of apogee. orbits, the orbital altitude, and defined according to the needs of a greater accuracy of the images collected, or with a greater amplitude of area to be coherent in each periodical passage in the same areas of interest to the orbital plane of the Earth, one can rotate the orbiter gradually along the annulus to compensate for the effect of the passage of Earth around the sun.

This ensures that the photographic images of a region will always be in the same conditions of sunlight, in addition to the work of photogrammetric and interpretation the successive generations of satellite image were improved in relation to the permanence period in orbit, for the adjustment of orbital parameters, to data transfer systems and in relation to payload.

While the first satellites recover their images in films that once exposed, were ejected and needed to be collected after their re-entry into the atmosphere, with the use of digital systems since the 1980s, photographs and other digital images were automatically transmitted to the station from ground to ground directly. This has led to an increase in the useful life of the satellites and greater agility in the collection and processing cycle.

Masint

Indeed, the area known as intelligence derived from generalizing in the United States since 1986, as an attempt to classify and agitate an array of activities, programs, and specialized agencies that are not easily accommodated in the most established collection practices of visual or communicative evidences from the use of the media.

The unification of this set of activities under the same rubric was due more to an organizational need than to some common trace between phenomena observed, or even among the technical merits used for monitoring.

In the North American context, they are part of the masin area from the collection and technical processing of hyper spectral and multispectral images, to the interception of telemetry signals from foreign missiles being tested, including the monitoring of geophysical phenomena (acoustic, seismic and magnetic by the measurement of levels of nuclear radiation in the earth's surface and in space by recording and analyzing unintentional radiation from electronic equipment and radars, and to stay here, by collecting and analyzing physic-chemical materials (effluents, particles, waste, parts of foreign equipment etc.).

According to Jeffrey Richelson 1999: 214-2401, at least three types of North American satellites carry dedicated sensors for the collection of masts: 1) The satellites of the DefInP Program IDSPI are equipped with infrared sensors (different from the sensors used for the production the data derived from these sensors allow the identification of the types of buses used and the spectral signatures associated with different systems of missiles. In theory, any terrestrial events that generate enough radioactivity infrared sensors to be detected from the space can be measured and identified by the DSP satellite sensors) NAVSTAR Global Positioning System (GPS) satellites are equipped with nuclear INUDETj.

Although the primary mission of NAVSTAR satellites is to provide accurate location data for target acquisition and navigation purposes, the orbit of the 17,700-kilometer orbit of the constellation of 21 NAVSTAR satellites has made the Pentagon also use for the global

monitoring of nuclear detonations, which can be detected by x-ray, gama and pulse electromagnetic.

Also, weather-using satellites IDMSpj are equipped with sensors for electromagnetic radiation and "tracking" of pieces of nuclear explosions in the atmosphere.

In addition to sensors installed in spacecraft, other technical means used by the United States for collecting masts involve airborne platforms for detecting and collecting samples of chemical and bacteriological agents in the atmosphere, fixed straps for monitoring missiles [such as the station radar "phased COBRA DANE, located on Shemya Island, Alaska], seismological laboratories at Air Force technical intelligence center, passive radars boarded on war ships, for monitoring of re - entry space vehicles, hydrophone undersea networks for acoustic monitoring submarines, and spacecraft over the ocean etc

Unfortunately, the limited information available on the nature of the masint activities pertains to that country. Such a diversity of means of collection and types of data collected stems not only from the technical-scientific complexity of the phenomena observed, but also of the scale of the operations and military forces of the United States.

One of the main functions of the masint area and the collection of information on singular characteristics - the signatures - of weapon systems, combat vehicles, aircraft, ships and radars for the assembly of databases and later employment in systems of acquisition of target, or for the production of military intelligence and monitoring of international treaties, especially in the nuclear area.

Osint

The dissemination of electronic bases accessible via the Internet has vastly increased the role of collecting intelligibility from more or less specialized ostensible sources. The charitable intelligence of ostensible sources or osint (open sources intelligence) has always been important to any governmental intelligence system, but there is a reasonable consensus in literature that its importance has recently grown in the context of the so-called "informational explosion" of intelligence.

In general, it consists of the legal issuance of official documents without security restrictions, direct and non-clandestine observation of political aspects. military, and economic aspects of the internal life of other countries or targets, the monitoring of media, radio and relaying, legal filing of specialized books and journals of a scientific and natural character, in a more or less extensive range of available sources and permitted in the strictest security restrictions.

When open political regimes and strict measures of security of a target for the circulation of information, plus the amount of intelligence potentially obtained from political programs,

Under the most restrictive conditions, the volume of available ostensible information tends to be very high. For example, it is now known that during the Cold War a joint program of the CIA and the U.S. Air Force summarized and / or fully translated most of the techno-scientific publications of the Soviet Union.

As early as 1956, \$ 50 meant the actual content of 328 scientific journals and about 3,000 books and monographs per year. With the end of the Cold War, the acceleration of the globalization and the advent of new information and communication technologies the availability of ostensible sources increased enormously.

According to the Deputy Director of Central Intelligence IDDCII, in 1992 the CIA foreign media watch service (O Foreign Broadcast Information Service - FBIS) monitored 790 hours of TV programming per week in 50 countries and 29 different languages. The FBIS monitoring events were then located in places as different as Abidjan, Aran, Asuncion, Bangkok, Panama City, Hong Kong, Islamabad, Key West, London, Mbabane, Nicosia, Okinawa, Seoul, Tel Aviv and Sierra. of techno-scientific publications and conventional media, in 1997 the CIA and OIA osint programs already had commercial access to nearly eight thousand databases of electronic data via the Internet, in addition to the signing of two thousand electronic journals? In the case of the United States, the main programs and offices available for the collection of ostensible information are the agencies and departments in charge of the analysis stage in the intelligence cycle.

Information Security and Counterintelligence

The most elementary operational dynamics of the area of ineligibility is also less understood by outside observers, and the one engendered from its conflict with the security measures that are taken by a potential target to protect its information. Starting from the restrictive practice of intelligence running the risk of exaggerated formalisation-while intelligence seeks to conquer what the co managers and rulers who direct it need to know about the problems and problems related to the identity of the State and the citizens, the area of information security , or information's security seeks to protect the information that, once obtained by an army or an enemy-for example, after the intelligence operations of a foreign govern could make the state and the citizens clear and unstable.

The area of intelligence and the area of security exert symmetrical and mutually dependent factors.

From the operational point of view, while the main task of the lobby area is to try to find the "or", the main part of the area of information and ensure that the "others" that we know what they know about us. The two objectives are fulfilled in the contemporary State by distinct organizations, and security can be considered as a managerial function in organizations and a responsibility of the command in military organizations. But psychosis

occurs because both activities exist simultaneously and interact in a more or less synergistic fashion for each actor involved in an informational conflict.

On the other hand, the dialectic between intelligence and security is more complex than the mere offensive dichotomy.

Information security can be thought of as consisting of three relatively autonomous components: ISCM security countermeasures. Counterintelligence [CI] and security of IOPSEq operations.

The first component is formed by the protective measures that "mirror" the adverse capacities of obtaining information. Such measures range from programs for the classification of government secrets, special storage, rules of custody and transfer of documents, physical restrictions on access to prisons and archives for unauthorized persons, investigations of personnel employed prior to the granting of credentials of access to the classified information and surveillance of their contacts with foreign and foreign personnel, the various policies and layers of electronic security in computer networks and the use of cryptography for the preservation of the segregation of communications (**comsec**).

In the military area, this set of ISCM countermeasures, or seizures, also includes the use of muffling to evade the signals of imminent enemy forces, reductions in intentional signatures and "signatures" "as measures against masint, training to withstand interrogatories and other preventive measures against the collection of humint.

Educational programs in the area of protection of knowledge fall into this first "family" of actions in the field of knowledge » the second set of measures of intelligence depends on the identification of intelligence operations of an adversary, the detection and neutralization of the intrusive means of obtaining information used by a government or organization considered hostile.

Although the traditional foe of the ICI counterintelligence area has been counter-espionage, the scope of the neutralization measures of intelligence gathering operations of an adversary goes far beyond the identification and repression of its humint collection networks.

As Michael Herman (1996: 168) wrote, an agent may be arrested, a foreign intelligence officer acting under diplomatic cover may be expelled from the country after being declared *persona non grata*, but also microphones and telephonic tapping may be " and can be felled or forced to save, collection races of **sigint** can be captured in case of breach of territorial waters, and so on.

For all these measures, knowledge accumulated by the counterintelligence area is fundamental.

Thirdly, due to the safety of the operations (hereinafter referred to as the set of procedures aimed at identifying which information on equipment, operations, capabilities and intentions would be critical for an individual to obtain.

However, in this analysis, it proposes a set of measures to actively deny such information to the Adviser. Although it also involves some programs for the reduction of noise and unintended signals, radio alerts, camouflage, and others, which could confuse this area of operational security stands out fundamentally for its active dimension, especially what military literature calls deception operations, used to mislead and induce an enemy to error through the use of accomplishment, deceit, concealment, and dissimulation, causing it to produce a misleading analysis of the situation.

Covered Operations

The so-called covert operations are named differently and cover varied activities in different countries, but have been widely used by major international potentials throughout the twentieth century, which is even more controversial than conventional moos intelligence operations. In the United States, these are called covert actions (CAs or covert Actions), and, in England, by the simple name of special political actions).

Although it is not possible to develop here a more complete analysis of the problems associated with this type of activity, at least one of these aspects deserves a brief summary. The first aspect relates to the types of operations encompassed by the concept, while the second aspect relates to the relationship between such covert operations and the collection activities analysis and counter-intelligence discussed here.

Covered events are used by a government or organization to attempt to systematically influence the behaviour of another government or organization through the manipulation of economic, social, and political aspects relevant to that actor, in a manner conducive to the interests and values of the organization or government it sponsors the operation.

The two main characteristics of the covert issues in the field of power are, according to Mark Lowenthal (2000: II-113) and Abram Shulsky (1992: 83-85), their instrumental character for policy implementation and the plausibility requirement for denial of authority.

The first feature is that covert operations as coercive tools in the implementation of an external policy, such as the one, for example, economic embargoes or the range of options relating to the use or threat of use of the force.

The second character emphasizes the denial of authorship, rather than the centrality of the operation itself. It is possible to classify the hidden operations according to the scale and intensity of the use of force means and the degree of plausibility of the denial of authorship.

Four types of covert operations can be selected.

- **The first type and the most extraneous, involving the membership of existing groups for financing and organizing groups for the war and underground warfare, paramilitary operations, guerrilla warfare, counter-terrorism or terrorism campaigns.** The involvement of a government in such cases can range from financial support and the provision of weapons, explosives, and equipment, to a more direct engagement in logistics, training, intelligence, and combat fighters specializing in special operations.""). Historical examples of such operations include, among many others, the "secret" war conducted by the United States in Laos 1960 -1975 and the British counter-insurgency campaign in Malaya 1950.

- **A second set of covert operations involves so-called "wet affairs",** ranging from support for coups d'état and attempted assassinations of leaders of the government forces, including irregular military operations at a border, sabotage and perpetration of acts terrorists. Examples of such operations are the CIA-sponsored coups in Iraq (1953) and Guatemala 1954, the American campaign of destabilization of the Allende government in Chile (1970-1973), the assassination of Palestinian leadership by the services Israeli secrets in the 1980s, or the sinking of Greenpeace's Rainbow Warrior by the French secret services in 1985.

- **The third type involves operations of economic and political sabotage against opposing forces or, on the other hand, governments and allied forces, such as political parties, neo-governmental organizations.** communication means etc.

The CIA campaign to prevent the victory of communists in the Italian elections of 1947 and an example of this type of operation. as well as the sale of weapons to Iraq (led by the United States presidency in 1986, with Israeli and Saudi intervention).

The training of the security forces and intelligence of the post-revolutionary regimes of the Yemen in the 1970s by the East German foreign intelligence service, or the help of the Soviet Union's Communist Party to about parties and groups in foreign countries until the 1980s.

On the other hand, the fourth type of covert operations comprises a set of measures to try to influence the perceptions of a government or even of society as a whole, through agents of influence, disinformation, and falsification of money or documents, in addition to the various types or types of transactions. This is the type of covert operation and there are examples, perhaps the most fertile ones were the Free Europe and Liberty radios, clandestinely established by the CIA in Europe in 1949 and 1951.